

Orbits with constant velocity on spherical shells

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Contents

1 The frictionless case	1
2 The friction case	5
3 Inversions to the frictionless case	11

1 The frictionless case

In a body of rotation is a ball.

A shell rotates, then a ball on the shell moves to a higher position. There are several questions. Is the ball in balance in this situation or does the ball fall down? Is there a free play? Are there areas in which the ball cannot stay? It's clear that the rotation velocity of the shell plays a major role in this situation. What is with other quantities? Which dependences are from this quantities? Are there quantities from which the situation is independent? The situation of a rotating shell is physical equivalent to a circling ball on a motionless shell. In all chapters the radius of the ball is very small compared to the measurements of

the spherical shell. We want to determine the dependence from r and v (velocity) and the angular velocity w , too. Gravitation and centrifugal force must be in balance. The centrifugal force often acts in everyday life. Everybody knows of the centrifugal force for example at a round-about or driving a curve. We view a shell of the ball. The angle of inclination of the inclined plane is α .

m = mass of the small interior ball

R_k = radius of the ball's shell (interior radius of the shell)

g = gravitation acceleration

$$\alpha = 90^\circ - (90^\circ - \gamma) = \gamma \quad \text{with that} \quad \alpha = \gamma$$

F_z = falling force

Z_z = centrifugal force against the falling force

$$F_z = mg \sin \alpha \quad \text{and} \quad Z_z = \frac{mv^2}{r} \cdot \cos \alpha$$

see the following figures:

F_N, Z_N are normal forces.

It follows:

$$Z_z = Z \cdot \cos \alpha \quad Z_N = Z \cdot \sin \alpha$$

we obtain:

$$Z_z = \frac{mv^2}{r} \cdot \cos \alpha \quad \alpha = \gamma$$

$$r = R_k \cdot \sin \alpha$$

insertion:

$$Z_z = \frac{mv^2}{R_k \cdot \sin \gamma} \cdot \cos \gamma$$

For F_z we get because of $\alpha = \gamma$:

$$F_z = mg \cdot \sin \gamma$$

For a stable orbit on the shell it must be $F_z = Z_z$ (balance), with that:

$$mg \sin \gamma = \frac{mv^2}{R_k \cdot \sin \gamma} \cdot \cos \gamma$$

transformed:

$$v^2 = g \cdot R_k \cdot \frac{\sin^2 \gamma}{\cos \gamma} \quad \text{with} \quad \frac{\sin \gamma}{\cos \gamma} = \tan \gamma$$

We get:

$$v(\gamma) = \sqrt{g \cdot R_k \cdot \sin \gamma \cdot \tan \gamma}$$

$$w = \frac{v}{r} \quad w = \text{angular velocity}$$

$$\begin{aligned} w(\gamma) &= \frac{\sqrt{g R_k \sin \gamma \tan \gamma}}{R_k \sin \gamma} = \sqrt{\frac{g R_k \sin \gamma \tan \gamma}{R_k^2 \cdot \sin^2 \gamma}} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{g \tan \gamma}{R_k \sin \gamma}} = \sqrt{\frac{g}{R_k \cdot \cos \gamma}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{time of rotation:} \quad U_t = \frac{2\pi}{w}$$

approximation:

For $\gamma \ll 90^\circ$ it is valid $\sin \gamma \approx \tan \gamma$

It follows:

$$v \approx \sqrt{g \cdot R_k \cdot \sin^2 \gamma} = \sin \gamma \cdot \sqrt{g \cdot R_k}$$

For γ near 90° we have $\sin \gamma \approx 1$:

$$v \approx \sqrt{g \cdot R_k \cdot \tan \gamma}$$

If the barycenter is the midpoint of the ball, we can do the following.

R = radius of the small ball

$R_k = R_i$ = radius of the shell of the ball (interior radius)

R_a = exterior radius

With the figure we obtain the relation:

$$r_m = r \cdot \frac{\sin \gamma \cdot R_k - \sin \gamma \cdot R}{\sin \gamma \cdot R_k} \quad (1)$$

With this we get:

$$r_m = r \cdot \frac{R_k - R}{R_k}$$

r_m of a small ball is less smaller than r .

If we insert r_m instead of r into the equations, we get the angular velocity and the velocity at the barycenter. We assume that the small ball has a (local) constant density. With the barycenter's correction we obtain the barycenter's velocity:

$$v_m = \sqrt{g \cdot r_m \cdot \tan \gamma} \quad \text{with} \quad r_m = R_k \cdot \sin \gamma \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R}{R_k}\right)$$

We get the velocity at the point of contact:

$$v = v_m \cdot \frac{R_k \cdot \sin \gamma}{r_m}$$

2 The friction case

We introduce the following notations:

m = mass of the ball

R = radius of the ball
 g = gravitation acceleration
 F_R = friction force
 μ = general friction coefficient
 μ_H = static friction coefficient
 μ_G = sliding friction coefficient
 μ' = rolling friction coefficient
 α = angle of inclination of the plane

We explain the factor δ in the following way:

$$\delta := \begin{cases} \frac{5}{7} & \text{if } \frac{\mu'}{R} < \mu_H \text{ (rolling)} \\ 1 & \text{if } \mu_H < \frac{\mu'}{R} \text{ (sliding)} \\ \frac{5}{7} \text{ or } 1 & \text{if } \frac{\mu'}{R} = \mu_H \neq 0 \text{ (decision is open)} \\ 1 & \text{if } 0 = \frac{\mu'}{R} = \mu_H \text{ (frictionless)} \end{cases}$$

See Assmann [1], volume 1, chapter 11.10, p. 265.

The acceleration b on the inclined plane is:

$b = \delta g \cdot \sin \alpha$, the velocity v and the distance s are $v = \delta g \sin \alpha \cdot t$ and $s = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \delta g \cdot t^2 \cdot \sin \alpha$.

If a ball is rolling on the inclined plane, it is $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$ see for example Budo [2], §57, p.302, equation (8). The moment of inertia J of a ball is $J = \frac{2}{5} \cdot mR^2$. The general formula for rolling on the inclined plane can be written as:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}} \quad (2)$$

One derivation can be found at * (at the end of chapter 2) or we can see this with Budo [2], §57, p.302, equations (5)-(7). With the moment of inertia of the ball we get:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{2}{5} \cdot m} = \frac{5}{7} \cdot g \sin \alpha \quad (3)$$

Then we get in the case of rolling $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$.

The forces are (see fig.):

$$F = mg \sin \alpha \quad F_N = mg \cos \alpha$$

friction force:

$$F_R = \mu \cdot F_N = mg \mu \cos \alpha$$

In the friction case is:

$$\mu = \begin{cases} \frac{\mu'}{R} & \text{if } \mu_H > \frac{\mu'}{R} \text{ (rolling)} \\ \mu_G & \text{if } \frac{\mu'}{R} > \mu_H \text{ (sliding)} \\ \mu_G \text{ or } \frac{\mu'}{R} & \text{if } \mu_H = \frac{\mu'}{R} \text{ (decision is open)} \end{cases}$$

See Assmann [1], volume 1, chapter 11.10, p.265. In the case of friction is:

$$F = mg \cdot (\delta \sin \alpha - \mu \cos \alpha) \quad b = g \cdot (\delta \sin \alpha - \mu \cos \alpha)$$

$$v = gt \cdot (\delta \sin \alpha - \mu \cos \alpha) \quad s = \frac{1}{2} \cdot gt^2 (\delta \sin \alpha - \mu \cos \alpha)$$

If we consider orbits on rotation bodies shells and Z is the centrifugal force, the inequality of stable orbits are see Sommerfeld [3], volume 1, §14.1, p.73:

$$Z_z - F_z \leq Z_R + F_R \quad F_z - Z_z \leq Z_R + F_R$$

with:

$$F_z = \delta mg \sin \alpha \quad F_R = mg \cos \alpha \cdot \mu$$

To the centrifugal forces (see fig.):

$$Z = \frac{mv^2}{r} = \text{centrifugal force}$$

$$Z_N = Z \cdot \sin \alpha \quad Z_z = \delta \cdot \frac{mv^2}{r} \cdot \cos \alpha$$

Z_R = friction force of the centrifugal force

$$Z_R = \mu \cdot Z_N = \mu \cdot \frac{mv^2}{r} \cdot \sin \alpha$$

Now we view orbits on the ball's shell with friction.

R_K = ball's radius (interior radius of ball's shell)

γ = height angle of the ball's shell

$\alpha = \gamma$

The limit velocities of stable orbits can be obtained with the following equations:

$$Z_z - F_z = Z_R + F_R \quad (4)$$

$$F_z - Z_z = Z_R + F_R \quad (5)$$

It is $r = \sin \gamma \cdot R_K$ and $\alpha = \gamma$. With (3) it follows:

$$\delta \cdot \frac{mv_{max}^2 \cos \gamma}{\sin \gamma \cdot R_K} - \delta mg \sin \gamma = \mu \frac{mv_{max}^2 \sin \gamma}{\sin \gamma \cdot R_K} + mg \cos \gamma \cdot \mu$$

with $\tan \gamma = \frac{\sin \gamma}{\cos \gamma}$ we get:

$$\frac{\delta mv_{max}^2}{\tan \gamma \cdot R_K} - \delta mg \sin \gamma = \frac{\mu mv_{max}^2}{R_K} + mg \cos \gamma \cdot \mu$$

ordered:

$$v_{max}^2 \cdot \left(\frac{\delta m}{\tan \gamma \cdot R_K} - \frac{\mu m}{R_K} \right) = mg \cos \gamma \cdot \mu + \delta mg \sin \gamma$$

Solving:

$$v_{max}^2 = \frac{g \sin \gamma \cdot \left(\delta + \frac{\mu}{\tan \gamma} \right)}{\left(\frac{\delta}{\tan \gamma} - \mu \right) \cdot \frac{1}{R_K}}$$

at last:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{g R_K \sin \gamma \cdot (\tan \gamma \cdot \delta + \mu)}{\delta - \mu \tan \gamma}}$$

With equation (4) we can get with the same method an expression of the minimum velocity:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{g R_K \sin \gamma \cdot (\delta \tan \gamma - \mu)}{\delta + \tan \gamma \cdot \mu}}$$

In general it is:

$$\text{angular velocity} = w = \frac{v}{r} = \frac{v}{\sin \gamma \cdot R_K}$$

It exists one γ_{max} and one γ_{min} , which can be determined in the following way with the maximum and minimum velocity.

$v_{max} = \infty$ if $\delta - \mu \tan \gamma = 0$, it follows:

$$\tan \gamma_{max} = \frac{\delta}{\mu}$$

$v_{min} = 0$ if $\delta \tan \gamma - \mu = 0$ from this we get:

$$\tan \gamma_{min} = \frac{\mu}{\delta}$$

We obtain in addition:

$$\gamma_{max} + \gamma_{min} = 90^\circ$$

With that the ball can move only in the interval $[\gamma_{min}, \gamma_{max}]$ in a stable orbit. Outside from this interval no stable orbits with constant height angle exist.

If we insert zero for μ we get from the maximum velocity and the minimum velocity the same expression

$$v = \sqrt{gR_K \sin \gamma \tan \gamma}$$

for the frictionless case. This is a known formula.

The relation between r and r_m is the same as in the frictionless case.

to *: The derivation of formula (1):

Notations:

kinetic energy = $E_{kin} = \frac{mv^2}{2}$

potential energy = $E_{pot} = mgh$ with $h = h_s \sin \alpha$ see fig.

rotational energy = $E_{rot} = \frac{Jw^2}{2}$ $J =$ moment of inertia

law of conservation of energy:

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jw^2}{2} = mgh$$

We assume that the body is only rolling not gliding. Then it is valid:

angular velocity = $w = \frac{v}{R}$ $R =$ radius of the rolling body

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jv^2}{2R^2} = mgh_s \sin \alpha$$

With transformation we get:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{2mgh_s \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}}$$

Because the rolling body has the constant acceleration $b = g \sin \alpha$, there is a uniform accelerated motion. For this motion it is valid: $v^2 = 2h_s \cdot b$ transformed to $b = \frac{v^2}{2h_s}$. Now we insert the equation of v :

$$b = \frac{2mgh_s \sin \alpha}{2h_s \cdot (m + \frac{J}{R^2})} = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}$$

Then we have the wanted formula.

3 Inversions to the frictionless case

The shell of the ball:

We take the same notation.

angular velocity:

$$w = \sqrt{\frac{g}{R_k \cdot \cos \gamma}} \quad \Rightarrow \quad w^2 = \frac{g}{R_k \cdot \cos \gamma}$$

transformed to $\cos \gamma$:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{g}{R_k \cdot w^2}$$

velocity formula:

$$v^2 = g \cdot R_k \cdot \sin \gamma \cdot \tan \gamma$$

with

$$\sin^2 \gamma + \cos^2 \gamma = 1 \quad \sin \gamma = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \gamma} \quad \tan \gamma = \frac{\sin \gamma}{\cos \gamma}$$

It follows:

$$v^2 = g R_k \cdot \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \gamma} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \gamma}}{\cos \gamma} = g R_k \cdot \frac{1 - \cos^2 \gamma}{\cos \gamma}$$

multiplying out:

$$v^2 \cos \gamma = g R_k - g R_k \cos^2 \gamma$$

At last we get an quadratic equation:

$$\cos^2 \gamma + \frac{v^2}{g R_k} \cdot \cos \gamma - 1 = 0$$

Solution of the quadratic equation:

$$\cos \gamma = +\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{v^2}{2g R_k}\right)^2} - \frac{v^2}{2g R_k}$$

Only the root with the positive sign makes sense, with a negative sign is $\cos \gamma < 0$ and in the interval $[0, 90^\circ]$ there is no solution.

References

- [1] Bruno Assmann "Technische Mechanik" volume 1 Oldenbourg Verlag
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- [2] A Budo "Theoretische Mechanik" 10.edition VEB Deutscher Verlag der
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- [3] Arnold Sommerfeld "Mechanik" volume 1 Verlag Harri Deutsch 8.edition
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